

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D1.2 Data Management Plan

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RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)

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COORDINATOR	Panagiotis Zervas
COORDINATOR EMAIL	panagiotis@scio.systems
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RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR EMAIL	antonis@scio.systems
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CONTRIBUTORS	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
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PARTICIPANTS		CONTACT PERSON
<p>SCiO P.C. (SCiO, Greece) Coordinator</p>		<p>Panagiotis Zervas E-mail: panagiotis@scio.systems</p>
<p>Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition, Agricultural University of Athens (AUA, Greece)</p>		<p>George-John Nychas E-mail: gjn@aua.gr</p>
<p>Department of Biotechnology and Food, Norwegian University of Science and Technology Science (NTNU, Norway)</p>		<p>Jørgen Lerfall E-mail: jorgen.lerfall@ntnu.no</p>
<p>Videometer A/S (VIDEOM, Denmark)</p>		<p>Nette Schultz E-mail: NS@videometer.com</p>
<p>Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition, University of Iceland (UoI, Iceland)</p>		<p>Maria Guðjónsdóttir E-mail: mariagu@hi.is</p>
<p>Matis (MATIS, Iceland)</p>		<p>Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir E-mail: hilduringa@matis.is</p>

ACRONYMS LIST

DMP	Data Management Plan
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report outlines how data and metadata will be collected, processed or generated in the context of the TraceMyFish Project. It also details on the provisions to ensure data integrity, security, privacy, and preservation, as well as the preliminary measures and directions to secure the maximum compliance of TraceMyFish data with the FAIR principles.

The Data Management Plan will be a living document that will be regularly updated by the project partners in order to align with the needs and requirements of the project. As the data needs and the operation of the TraceMyFish data platform is concretised, updated versions of this document will be provided, updating all the sections affected by the developments and findings of the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The purpose of deliverable D1.2 - Data Management Plan is to describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the TraceMyFish project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), the project's Data Management Plan (DMP) includes information on the handling of research data during & after the end of the project; what data will be collected, processed and/or generated; which methodology & standards will be applied; whether data will be shared/made open access; how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

1.2 APPROACH FOR WP AND RELATION TO OTHER WPS AND DELIVERABLES

The data-centric nature of TraceMyFish puts Data Management at the core of all major activities. It is informed by the data needs elicited from the requirements definition process in the context of WP2; it determines the architectural and technical choices for designing and operationalising the TraceMyFish sensor technologies (WP3), developing the AI models to be enacted (WP4) and implementing the TraceMyFish Data Platform (WP5); it informs the way that TraceMyFish pilots will collect and handle data during their execution (WP6); and finally, it dictates how scientific and pilot data are published, disseminated and communicated in different contexts and venues (WP7).

As a result, the Data Management Plan is bidirectionally linked to all work packages, needing their input to properly define the data needs and the expectations from their usage and providing the template to organize all data-centric activities in the work packages and the project as a whole.

1.3 METHODOLOGY AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The deliverable is structured in accordance with the template and guidelines provided by the EC, and is organized in the following sections: Section 2 provides a data summary addressing issues regarding the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project, the types and formats of data the project will generate/collect, the origin of data, the expected size of data, and the data utility (i.e., to whom might it be useful). Section 3 reports on the measures and directions to be adopted to ensure the compliance of TraceMyFish with FAIR data principles. Section 4 summarizes the allocation of resources and a preliminary cost coverage plan in the context of the project, in order to serve the aforementioned measures. Section 5 discusses on the main concerns regarding data security and privacy and the proposed approaches to face them, while Section 6 discusses ethical and legal aspects related to the data involved in the project.

2 DATA SUMMARY

The following subsections present a high-level summary of the types of data items produced, processed or managed by each relevant TraceMyFish work package.

2.1 WP2 DATASETS

The main data items expected to be produced by WP2, *Tracking hazards & potential measures*, are those produced by the requirements elicitation processes carried out via questionnaires and expressed in structured and unstructured reports. While these do not pose any substantial requirements in terms of storage or processing, they will be one of the key concerns for compliance with the GDPR and other legislations and guidelines referring to the management of personal and sensitive data. The TraceMyFish approach for fulfilling such requirements is described in Section 5 of the DMP.

2.2 WP3 DATASETS

WP3, *Detecting and monitoring tools*, is the core TraceMyFish work package with respect to spectral imaging data production. In the context of its tasks, data will be generated firstly in the context of the sensor calibration and performance assessment experiments and, to a larger extent, in the context of the data acquisition activities for the TraceMyFish pilots. The exact derived features of the collected data will be determined upon finalization of the requirements elicitation process, which will identify the key sensing data to be tracked by TraceMyFish. Indicatively, the datasets may incorporate measurements for temperature, colour, pH, water-holding properties, texture, proximate composition, content of parasites, and microbiological counts that may be derived from the spectral imaging data acquisition. In the case of pilot data, these will be accompanied by tracking information, both geospatial and temporal.

2.3 WP4 DATASETS

The main objective of WP4, *AI models for tracking and tracing*, is the development and deployment of the AI/ML models to be incorporated in the TraceMyFish iFMS. As a consequence, the core data objects to be produced by the Work Package fall under the following categories:

1. Data derived from laboratory experiments to establish the training datasets for the TraceMyFish AI models
2. Synthetic training data in case they are deemed as necessary for the effective training of the models
3. The source code of the scripts implementing the AI/ML models, along with their documentation

Additionally, the work package is expected to produce scientific publications and articles presenting the findings of the analytical activities carried out. The management of code and scientific assets is presented in section 2.6 and 2.7 of the DMP.

2.4 WP5 DATASETS

WP5, TraceMyFish Data Ecosystem, is a primarily technical and engineering-driven work package. As such, it does not produce any substantial data volumes of any kind. Nevertheless, this is the work item responsible for designing and developing the project's data management platform. Consequently, work on the package is heavily influenced by the DMP, and it will incorporate all required processes and modules to ensure data privacy, security and integrity. This also extends to the development of the APIs exposing data to client applications, which will incorporate the necessary AAI functionalities to ensure that anyone accessing the data has the authority and permission to do so. Furthermore, it is responsible for integrating the sub-components for the updating of the information exposed via the smart barcodes accompanying the products.

2.5 WP6 DATASETS

WP6, *Piloting and evaluation*, is closely associated in terms of data management with WPs 3 and 5, as data collection and processing in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots will be carried out in the context of WP3 and

use the technologies provided by WP5. In this sense, sensing and geolocation data collection and processing do not fall under this work package and are to be covered by other work items. WP6 itself will be responsible for collecting and aggregating the pilot evaluation data, and thus called to comply to the data privacy guidelines of the project. Furthermore, any scientific publications to be produced will be managed in accordance to the DMP (cf. next section, 2.6).

2.6 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

As described, scientific publications are expected to be produced as outputs of work packages 2, 4 and 6 of TraceMyFish, but also as an outcome of the overall project activities. In accordance with EC directives and the Grant Agreement, scientific publications produced in TraceMyFish will be made available under Green Open Access models, and accessible via the project's and partners' portals. Upon decision, certain publications may be published under Gold Open Access and consequently available via the publisher's website. In any case, pre-prints of publications will be submitted to relevant archiving services such as Zenodo and arXiv.

2.7 SOURCE CODE

In principle, the source code for software developed in the context of TraceMyFish will be openly available under appropriate licenses, to be selected per case. Publishable source code will be accessible via a central repository hosted in popular relevant services like GitHub or GitLab, with the possibility that the consortium uses repositories accessible only to TraceMyFish partners for development and testing purposes.

The VideometerLab software source code, developed for VideometerLab and VideometerLite instruments constitute Videometer's proprietary assets and will not be open-sourced.

Similarly, the AI platform for testing and optimizing the AI models to be used in the project constitute SCiO's proprietary assets and will not be open-sourced.

As the project evolves, the DMP will incorporate details on the services and repositories used for distributing, documenting, and supporting the source code.

3 FAIR PRINCIPLES

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVENANCE FOR METADATA

For the fair access of the project data a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be requested for each artefact. In more details, DOIs from Crossref will be used for research publications, while DOIs from DataCite will be pursued for labelling each dataset of the project. In addition, a metadata record for each output of the project will be created and stored in the data directory. Amongst other fields, each metadata record will have a set of keywords that will make searches easier for external parties. Each data source will be provided with a specific name that is composed by different parts/elements, containing information about pilot, country, data type or format and naming structure.

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Several datasets that will be used as part of the project will be offered by third-party providers. Some of these datasets are already open to the public, while others are proprietary and have high commercial sensitivity. In the cases where private data are processed and aggregated (e.g., as part of a model, or functionality of a component) permission will be requested by the provider prior to making the altered data publicly available. In reference to the nature of the user data involved, some of the results that will be generated by each project phase will be restricted to authorised users, while other results will be publicly available. As per our Ethics commitment during the negotiation phase of the project, data access and sharing activities will be rigorously implemented in compliance with the privacy and data collection rules and regulations, as they are applied nationally and in the EU.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

As TraceMyFish will be making use of variegating data sources along with the data generated by the project itself, interoperability is a major challenge to be tackled for making the TraceMyFish platform operational. The challenge will be met primarily via the extensive usage of semantic web technologies, where applicable, and the incorporation of standards and widely used schemas, ontologies and vocabularies for describing TraceMyFish data assets. Furthermore, data will be made available via standard-based APIs where applicable. In the same fashion, external data sources will be ingested via their APIs when such services are present. Relevant documentation for the way data is represented will be included in all cases and will be made available following the same approach as the project's source code, i.e., via publicly accessible repositories.

3.4 INCREASE DATA REUSE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES)

If possible, TraceMyFish datasets will be licensed under an Open Access license. However, this will depend on the level of privacy, and the Intellectual Property Right (IPR) involved in the data primarily by pilot partners. A period of embargo will only be necessary if a data set contains specific IPR or other exploitable results that will justify an embargo. Therefore, the data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible when no limitations are identified by the key stakeholders.

The intention of TraceMyFish is to make as much data as possible reusable for third parties. Restriction will only apply when privacy, IPR, or other exploitations ground are in play. All datasets will be cleared of bad records, with clear naming conventions, and with appropriate metadata.

All data generated and collected in TraceMyFish will undergo a quality check in order to analyse its individual plausibility and consistency, making sure that others can directly use it to perform assessments and validate the research carried out by the project. As in some cases similar results will be generated for different case studies, data harmonisation will also be of critical importance both for increasing data reuse in general, but also to ease the comparison of results in the TraceMyFish pilots.

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Data Management is a core overarching activity for TraceMyFish, as data collection and processing inform all its technical activities. Structurally, the activity is the focus of Task T1.2, led by SCiO. In any case, effort on Data Management will be also dedicated in work packages 2-6 that deal with data collection, processing and generation. Regarding additional costs emerging from the adopted approach for data and knowledge publishing, the following table provides a high-level summary.

Table 1: Handling of Additional Cost Items

Issue	Action
Costs for making non-patented data FAIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Fees associated with the publication of scientific articles containing project research data in “Gold” Open Access journals. The cost sharing in case of multiple authors will be decided among the authors on a per case basis. b. Project website operation: costs covered by UoI c. Data archiving at Zenodo/OpenAIRE: free of charge d. Copyright licensing with CC: free of charge
Partner responsibilities	Every partner is responsible for the data they produce. Any fee incurred for Open Access through scientific publication of the data will be the responsibility of the data owner (authors) partner(s) in compliance with the CA.
Long-term preservation	Data preservation of at least 1 year after the project, in accordance with EC practices and requirements. The associated costs for dataset preparation for archiving will be covered within the project itself. Long-term preservation of code and open datasets will be provided, and associated costs covered by a selected disciplinary repository. Proprietary and sensitive datasets will remain the property of the owners.

5 DATA SECURITY AND PROTECTION

5.1 SECURITY SCOPE IN THE CONTEXT OF TRACEMYFISH

While data security is not critical within the project itself, TraceMyFish aspires to produce a close-to-market solution at its end. Thus, data security and integrity are of paramount importance for the project. Security requirements stem, on the one hand, from the association of personal and geospatial information with the collected sensing information and, on the other hand, the need to ensure the integrity and trustworthiness of the collected measurements. This will be achieved via the incorporation of security measures in all communication mechanisms incorporated in the TraceMyFish data platform, the deployment of immutable ledger infrastructure for storing and preserving sensing data, as well as the decentralisation of storage and particularly with respect to measurements and user information. In this way, multiple and coordinated breaches would be required to actually acquire or modify information related to a user/chain and a single point of security failure will never exist in the TraceMyFish data workflow.

5.2 DATA PROTECTION AND GDPR COMPLIANCE

To ensure that risks related to privacy and sensitivity of information are mitigated, all partners involved in the processing of personal data will be required to apply the appropriate data protection measures as outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation. These may include the collection of consent forms by the contacted individuals, the formulation of appropriate privacy policies and the incorporation of secure registration, authentication and authorization mechanisms for the project's platforms and services.

TraceMyFish will pay particular attention to the protection of personal data, to maximize its utility in compliance with applicable legislation relating to the protection of personal data. The TraceMyFish project shall ensure that no data will be shared without ensuring legal compliance and calculating legal risks. In particular, the TraceMyFish project shall ensure that personal data are protected according to the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and that the use cases and experiments developed adhere to the GDPR. This refers mainly to the provision of consent forms in cases where individuals are contacted in the context of dissemination activities and to the provision of a clear and comprehensive terms of use document for registering in the platform. In principle, no data will be shared or sold to any third party, and any personal information will be used only within the context of the TraceMyFish iFMS. Anonymous aggregate statistics will be collected and used for improving the AI models incorporated in the platform, upon user consent.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

At the moment of preparation of the initial version of the DMP, no ethical or further issues were identified. Any issue that may emerge during the course of the project will be reported and addressed at updated versions of the DMP.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The present report describes the data management lifecycle for the data to be collected, processed and generated in the context of TraceMyFish. As part of the pursue to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), it focuses on the handling of research data during & after the end of the project; what data will be collected, processed and/or generated; which methodology & standards will be applied; whether data will be shared/made open access; how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

The current deliverable is the initial version of the project's DMP, which will be treated as a live document from hereon; as the project evolves, the report will be revised and updated providing further details and - if needed - amendments and corrections to make sure that all data-related aspects of TraceMyFish are covered thoroughly and in accordance with the guiding principles of FAIRness, security and privacy.